

Comparative Morphohistological Study of Nasal Salt Gland in Three Water Birds Coot Birds (*Gallinula silvestris*), Domestic Geese (*Anser anser domesticus*), and Domestic Ducks (*Anas platyrhynchos*)

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Abstract:

Background: The study's objective is to ascertain the comparative morphohistological features of salt gland of three species of birds, coot bird, duck and goose. Eighteen adult, healthy birds of each of the following sexes species (six birds for each species). **Result:** The frontal bone's supraorbital depression contains well-developed bilateral salt glands that are located beneath the skin in both species. The gland was ranged in color from pinkish white to reddish brown. in duck and goose were crescent in shaped, it was irregular or amebae-shaped, in the coot bird. Histological salt gland was covered by a thin capsule of connective tissue and comprise a large number of rows of concentric polygonal lobes divided by heavily vascularized interlobular connective tissue. Every lobe is composed of branching

secretory tubules that are enmeshed with connective tissue that is rich in blood capillaries and lined with a single layer of cuboidal cells oriented radially from a central canal. Every lobe's duct system empties into the central canal, which empties into a primary duct that travels to the nasal cavity's anterior region. **Conclusion:** This study indicated that the three species of avian salt gland had distinctive histological structures, which helped to understand the impact of each species' habits and actions on this gland's development.

Keywords: *Histology, Morphology, Salt gland.*

Introduction

Water birds, snakes, and crocodiles are just a few of the animal species that rely on their nasal glands, also known as salt glands, as a vital adaptation mechanism (14). Salt from the blood is concentrated in and expelled by the nasal gland in birds. In numerous aquatic birds (e.g., Spheniciformes, Charadriiformes, Precelariiformes, Anseriformes, Pelecaniformes, Phoenicopteriformes), The nasal gland is hypertrophied and resides supraorbitally, while it is also known to exist in various sites in birds, such as the orbit (suliforms, for example)

(Bokenes, 1998; Jarrar, & Basher, 2009; Maysoon, 2011; Reshag, Abood, & Mohammed, 2016).

When seawater is consumed, nasal glands that secrete salt create sodium chloride solutions that are hypertonic in response to osmotic loads. This gland's existence is viewed as essential adaptation mechanism in birds, which live in a salty atmosphere concentration (10, 4). When it comes to the body's elimination and secretion of salt, the salt gland is more significant than the kidney (17, 11, 12). The glandular lobes on both sides of the salt glands include secretory lobules

encased in a connective tissue capsule, comprising a range of branching secretory tubule arrangements radially for each lobe from the central canal and are intertwined blood capillaries in one layer of cells. The secretory tubule is composed of segments of rounded basal cells at the terminal end of a narrow lumen surrounded by basic cuboidal-columnar epithelium and a primary duct leading to the anterior of the nasal cavity serves as the drainage system for the secretory tubules and central canals (Maysoon, 2011). The objective of the current study was to compare the morphological and histological structures of the salt gland in three different types of birds: duck, goose, and coot.

Material and Method

Eighteen mature, healthy birds of both sexes—six coots, six ducks, and six geese—were gathered from the local markets in the provinces of Basra. Every bird was decapitated, its salt glands swiftly extracted, morphometric measurements were made, the birds were submerged in 10% neutral buffered formalin, passed through a succession of graded alcohols, xylene, and finally embedded in paraffin wax. Hematoxylin and eosin stain Bancroft, & Marily, (2002) was used to produce and stain the paraffin slices, which were between five and six μm thick. One-way ANOVA was used for the statistical analysis of this study.

Result

Macroscopic Aspect

The macroscopic aspect revealed that the salt gland in three species of these birds which were securely linked with a depression above the orbits in the frontal bone, The glands were directly covered by the skin of the head. Duck and goose morphological salt glands are crescent-shaped, with two pointed anterior and posterior extremities; the ventral boarder, which faces the eyeball, is concave, while the dorsal boarder is carved, it was irregular or amebea – shaped, in the coot bird, glands ranged in color

from pinkish white to reddish brown figure (1, 2, 3).

Morphometrical Studies

Morphometric analyses Statistical descriptions of the (dimensions: length, width, and thickness) of salt gland in domestic duck, goose and coot bird were recorded in table (1)

The mean of all lengths in duck, goose, and coot birds measured 1.55, 1.57, and 1.24 cm, in that order. In ducks, goose, and coots, the mean width of the gland was 0.95 cm, 0.95 cm, and 0.70 cm, respectively. In ducks, the gland's mean thickness was 0.39 cm; in geese, it was 0.37 cm; and in coots, it was 0.20 cm.

Microscopic aspect: Histological investigation of the salt gland in both species of these birds was enclosed by a a narrow capsule of connective tissue containing blood arteries, collagen, fibroblasts, and elastic fibers. Thin septae of connective tissue protruded from the capsule into the gland, dividing the parenchyma into irregular, polygonal zones known as lobes and lobules. The salt gland of the coot bird in the present study is lobulated and surrounded by thin bundles of connective tissue fibers. Every glandular lobule contained a compound tubuloacinar secretory unit lined with simple columnar epithelium tissue, and its secretion was mucoserous material. This was covered by the lobule duct, which was followed by the main duct, both of which were lined with low, simple cuboidal epithelium tissue. As well as the parenchymal glandular lobe, the samcin was peripheral and central to the lobe (Figure 4).

The salt gland of local geese was covered with a thin capsule in this study. The gland receives septa from this capsule, which divides it into lobes and lobules, which are complex tubulealveolar and empty into a large lumen. The mode of secretion was porcine. These glands are made up of high columnar epithelial cells. Cells in the apex glandular epithelium were darkly stained and secreted serous fluid, whereas cells in the deep glandular epithelium were faintly stained and secreted mucous fluid. The glandular end piece's neck included mucine-producing cells with defined cell boundaries. A single

centrally positioned duct with an uneven lumen. The duct epithelium included many layers and a variety of cell shapes. The main duct's basal layer cells were polygonal, while the cells close to the lumen were cuboidal. These cell positions and shapes were shifting throughout the duct. In between these cells, goblet cells were scattered. The parenchyma was separated into lobules of various sizes by septa of connective tissue that protruded from the blood vessel and nerve capsule figure (5).

These lobules manifested as multilateral zones in a duck with a central canal. The secretory acini that comprised each lobule were only sporadically connected by connective tissue. Simple columnar epithelium with vacuolated cytoplasm bordered the central lumen of the duck and schemed into the central tubule duct. These folds that resembled villi were united and branched. According to the current study, the domestic duck's tubules are entirely lined by a single layer of tall columnar cells that stain

uniformly. Their massive nuclei were located close to the cells' bases. Poorly pigmented and filled with dispersed granules that could be easily distinguished from cell boundaries, the cytoplasm. The characteristics of salt gland related geese and ducks were examined in this study figure (6).

Table 1. Descriptive Data on the Length, Width, and Thickness of the Salt Glands in Three Birds, Measured in Centimeters

Group	Length\cm	Width\cm	thickness
Du	1.55 ±0.047	0.95 ±0.108	0.39±0.057
Go	1.57 ±0.11	0.95 ±0.108	0.37 ±0.07
Co	1.24 ±0.126	0.70 ±0.06	0.20 ± 0.07
LSD	0.22	0.11	0.11

Table (1) mean of length, width and thickness of salt gland in three species of birds (duck (du) goose (go) and coot bird (co)).

Figure 1. Macrograph of Coot Bird Head (a. salt gland, b. skull)

Figure 2. Macrograph of Goose Head (a. salt gland, b. skull)

Figure 3. Macrograph of Duck Head (a. salt gland, b. skull)

Figure 4. Histological Section of the Salt Gland: (A) in Coot bird had a thin capsule made of adipose tissue (ad) that covered the duct (D) inter lobular septa(in) (H&E stain x10). (B) shows duct (D) corpus gland (cg) cuboidal cells lining (cu) (H&E stain x40)

Figure 5. A, B Histological portion of The geese salt gland was shown to have lobules (L) made of secretory acini (Ac) wrapped in a capsule (arrow) that had septa (S), blood arteries (B), and other structures and irregular lumen of duct(I), light cells and dark cells (zigzag arrow).H&E X 10, X 40

Figure 6. C,D Histological section of The salt gland in duck revealed the lobules (L) made of secretory acini (Ac) that were encased in a capsule (arrow) that had septa (S), irregular duct lumen (I), and blood vessels (b). H&E X 10, X 40

Discussion

Across examination of the current research proved that the salt glands of three species of The crescent shape (duck, goose) and supraorbital location of birds were as similar as what was indicated in the majority of water birds, including flamingos, moor hens, common coots, and ducks, which were researched by Al-Mansour, (2009); Hussein, Hussein, & Mustafa, (2006); Maysoon, (2011) and Reshag, Abood, & Mohammed, (2016). For the most part, the salt gland's shape in coot birds was irregular or

amebean in shape, as mentioned in the present study. The hue of the glands varied from reddish brown to pinkish white. The color of the salt-stressed gland was dark red, whereas the gland color of freshwater ducks was pale red (El-Gohary, et al., 2013). This observation of the shift in color of the salt gland from red to dark red in birds that drink salt-loaded water was made earlier. According to the current study, the shaft and increased blood flow toward the gland when the bird drank saline water may have caused this change in gland color. The current

study suggested that the cause of such an alteration in gland color was the shaft and increased blood flow toward the gland when the bird drank salty water. All domestic ducks and geese that were studied had salt glands that were in accordance with the macromorphometry described by Bokenes, (1998), who saw that the gland had dimensions of 1.5 cm in length, 0.90 cm in width, and 0.5 cm in thickness. The present work revealed that the histological examination of the A composite tubuloacinar connective tissue capsule lined with simple columnar cells encircled the salt gland.

All of the birds in our study had simple columnar secretory epithelium lining the central collecting duct in their salt glands; these findings were comparable to those of Hussein, Hussein, & Mustafa, (2006), Jarrar, & Basher, (2009), Reshag, Abood, & Mohammed, (2016), Waleed, (2016). They demonstrated how the salt glands of several bird species are made up of multiple longitudinal lobules made up of secretory tubules that extend from central canals. Principle and basal cells lined the secretory tubules. In the present work, the salt gland coot bird consists of many acino tubular units. These simple columnar epithelium tissues lined with its secretion were seromucose material. This excretal with Schmidt-Nielsen, & Fange, (1958), Schmidt-Nielsen, & Kim, (1964) as well as in domestic geese the duct epithelium was multi-layered, and the cell shape varied, with the main duct being pentagonal and the ones around the lumen being cuboidal. The duct was centrally situated and had an asymmetrical lumen (Fange, Schmidt-Nielsen, & Osaki, 1958). Histological picture of the Three different bird species had simple cuboidal epithelium tissue lining their salt glands: coots, ducks, and geese. These birds also had simple columnar epithelium lining their main duct and interlobular duct. On the other hand, Fange, Schmidt-Nielsen, & Osaki, (1958) in capercaillie, Japanese quails, and Al-Mansour, (2009) in osprey reported Primary ducts had a large lumen that was lined with columnar epithelial cells that varied in height, and secondary ducts had a layer of cuboidal cells.

Conclusion

In summary, the three bird species exhibited distinct characteristics, and the morphology and histology of the salt gland were generally similar but not identical.

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